

Bisiminocamphor Derivatives with Exalted Optical Activity.

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Forster and Thornley (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, **95**, 942) observed that bisiminocamphor derivatives display remarkably high rotatory power, and this was later ascribed to an optimum association of azethenoid groups, conjugated linkages and a benzene ring within a narrow molecular compass (Forster and Spinner, *ibid.*, 1919, **115**, 889). B. K. Singh and his collaborators also have prepared numerous bisiminocamphor derivatives (*ibid.*, 1919, **115**, 566; 1920, **117**, 1599; 1921, **119**, 1971 ; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **3**, 385; 1929, **6**, 107; 1930, **7**, 545, 771; 1931, **8**, 95, 181, 345, 623; 1932, **9**, 1) including 1:4-naphthylenebisiminocamphor and *pp'*-bisiminocamphordiphenylamine, with molecular rotation 13416° (pyridine) and 14231° (ethyl alcohol) respectively. These two compounds, within a narrow molecular compass, embrace two azethenoid groups and included in their naphthalene or benzene rings conjugated double linkages aggregating nine and ten respectively, thus confirming the above-quoted generalisation.

Maintaining the foregoing typical molecular arrangement, we have now prepared 1:4-naphthylenebisiminobenzylideneiminocamphor in

(I)

which the number of conjugated double linkages has been increased to 17; correspondingly, the molecular rotation reaches 22050° in pyridine for the mercury yellow line 5780. This observation was made in collaboration with Mr. S. M. Mistry and communicated to the Indian Science Congress, 1931.

The preparation of this compound followed some unsuccessful attempts. An obvious method would be to condense with 1:4-naphthylenediamine two molecules of the condensation product of *p*-aminobenzaldehyde with camphorquinone, but the latter could not be obtained owing to the readiness with which the aldehyde undergoes polymerisation (*cf.* Gabriel, *Ber.*, 1883, 16, 2000). The next attempt was to proceed through *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde according to the following scheme :

The acid reduction of bisnitrobenzylidenenaphthylenediamine could not be effected, the azomethine group being very sensitive to mineral acids, while reduction with alcoholic ammonium sulphide, zinc dust and acetic acid or ferrous sulphate and ammonia yielded only tarry products.

Finally, we condensed *p*-acetaminobenzaldehyde with 1:4-naphthylenediamine, removed the acetyl groups by dilute hydrochloric acid in

alcohol, and condensed the resulting bisaminobenzylidenenaphthylenediamine with camphorquinone as follows:

It is well known that the carbonyl group exalts optical rotation in organic compounds (*cf.* Hilditch, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 99, 224) and it seemed of interest to ascertain the effect on rotation produced by interrupting a conjugated system with a carbonyl or a carbamido group. The introduction of a carbonyl, carbamido or an oxamido group between two benzene rings in *pp*-diphenylene-bisiminocamphor from benzidine and camphorquinone, and a comparison of the resulting rotations with those of the corresponding compounds of benzidine and diaminodiphenylmethane would indicate the effect of such groups combined with interruption of conjugation.

While *pp'*-diaminobenzophenone* could not be condensed with camphorquinone, the bisiminocamphor derivative of *pp*-diaminodiphenylcarbamide and *pp*-diaminodiphenyloxamide show the following rotations, the values comparing very favourably with that of the benzidine compound; it is thus clear that the decrease caused by breaking the continuity of conjugated double bonds is more than compensated by the introduction of the carbamido and the oxamido groups.

* For dissimilar behaviour of diaminodiphenylmethane and diaminobenzophenone compare Guha and Mistry (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1932, 15A, 27).

(II)

(III)

Resembling *pp*-diaminobenzophenone, *pp*-diaminoazobenzene (i), *pp*-diaminodiphenylazodicarbonamide (ii), 1:4-diaminoanthraquinone (iii), and bisaminophenylanthraquinonedimide (iv), could not be made to react with camphorquinone; the compounds sought, particularly that from the last named, were expected to show very high rotatory power.*

EXPERIMENTAL.

Condensation of p-nitrobenzaldehyde with 1:4-naphthylenediamine.—The naphthylenediamine was prepared by coupling diazotised aniline with α -naphthylamine and reducing the product with zinc and boiling water (*Ber.*, 1889, 22, 1381). To naphthylenediamine hydrochloride (2.4 g.) dissolved in a little water, crystalline sodium acetate was added in excess. *p*-Nitrobenzaldehyde (3.5 g.) in 95% alcohol

* These experiments were conducted in collaboration with Mr. S. M. Mistry and a preliminary report published in the *Proc. Indian Science Cong.*, 1932, p. 220.

was then added and the mixture heated under reflux for 3 hours when gradually the dinitro-compound separated as a reddish-yellow precipitate which was washed with hot alcohol and recrystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 281°. (Found: N, 13.04. $C_{24}H_{16}O_4N_4$ requires N, 13.2 per cent).

Attempts to reduce the dinitro compound.—Reducing agents involving the use of mineral acids could not be used because they attacked azomethine group. Reduction was successively tried with alcoholic ammonium sulphide, sodium sulphide and water, zinc dust and glacial acetic acid and lastly with ferrous sulphate and ammonia. The ethereal extract of the free diamine exhibited in all cases a green fluorescence and on evaporation of ether left only a tarry semi-solid mass.

Condensation of p-acetaminobenzaldehyde with 1:4-naphthylenediamine.—The yellow crystalline acetamino compound was obtained by boiling *p*-aminobenzaldehyde hydrochloride with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate (*Monatsh.*, 1903, 24, 88), m.p. 154-55° (not 161° as given in the literature).

A solution of naphthylenediamine hydrochloride (2.3 g.) in water, excess of sodium acetate and acetaminobenzaldehyde (3.5 g.) in 95% alcohol was heated under reflux for 2 hours. The precipitated greenish powder crystallised from pyridine in brown needles, m.p. 317°. (Found: N, 12.6. $C_{28}H_{24}O_2N_4$ requires N, 12.5 per cent).

Hydrolysis of the acetyl compound.—Hydrolysis could not be effected by boiling with *N*/2, 2*N*, and 5*N* alcoholic potash, while stronger alkali gave tarry products. The diacetyl compound was next mixed with a small quantity of alcohol and treated with dilute hydrochloric acid, forming a clear solution on being gently warmed; this was cooled in ice and treated with ice-cold concentrated hydrochloric acid when the hydrochloride of bis-*pp*-aminobenzylidenenaphthylenediamine was obtained as a yellowish-red crystalline product. (Found: N, 13.12. $C_{24}H_{22}N_4Cl_2$ requires N, 12.81 per cent).

1:4-Naphthylenebisiminobenzylideneiminocamphor (I).—The hydrochloride of bis-*pp*-aminobenzylidene-1:4-naphthylenediamine (4.3 g.) mixed with water and excess of sodium acetate was treated with camphorquinone (3.5 g.) in 95% alcohol and boiled for 2 hours. On cooling, deep-red crystals were deposited which after being washed with water and petrol crystallised from absolute alcohol, m.p. 239°. (Found: N, 8.6. $C_{44}H_{44}O_2N_4$ requires N, 8.4 per cent). The rotation observed for 0.1100 g. of the substance

dissolved in 250 c.c. of dry pyridine in a 1 dcm. tube was $\alpha_{5780} = 1.47^\circ$, whence $[\alpha]_{5780}^{25^\circ} = 3340.9^\circ$, corresponding to $[M]_{5780}^{25^\circ} = 22050^\circ$.

An improved method of preparing pp'-diaminodiphenylcarbamide.—The method of Schiff and Ostrogovitsch (*Annalen*, 1896, 293, 376) gave a very poor yield most of which was, however, insoluble in boiling concentrated hydrochloric acid. The condensation of acet-*p*-phenylenediamine with urea proceeded quite smoothly according to the method of Guha and Mistry (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 8, 793) in boiling amyl alcohol, evolution of ammonia terminating after 7 hours. The pure colourless diacetyl compound melted at 348° .

Hydrolysis could not be effected by boiling for a long time with dilute hydrochloric acid, but the powdered acetyl compound dissolved in gently boiling concentrated hydrochloric acid for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The filtered solution on concentration gave a white crystalline hydrochloride.

Diaminodiphenylcarbamide and camphorquinone: Formation of carbamidodiphenylenebisiminocamphor (II).—A mixture of diaminodiphenylcarbamide hydrochloride (1.6 g.), excess of sodium acetate and camphorquinone (3.5 g.) in 95% alcohol was boiled under reflux for 2 hours when the solution became deep red. The greenish yellow precipitate obtained on adding water was washed with petrol to remove camphorquinone and yielded on careful crystallisation from alcohol two isomeric compounds (A and B). The substance (A) was nearly insoluble in alcohol and was obtained as a greenish precipitate after several crystallisation from 98% alcohol, m.p. 280° . Compound (B) was obtained as an orange powder after crystallisation from 70% alcohol, m.p. 266° . (Found: (A) N, 10.2; (B) N, 10.4. $C_{33}H_{38}O_3N_4$ requires N, 10.4 per cent). 0.2110 G. of the substance (A), dissolved in 25 c.c. of chloroform gave in 0.5 dcm. tube $\alpha_D 6.99^\circ$, corresponding to $[M]_D = 8911.4^\circ$. On account of the sparing solubility of (B) in solvents its molecular rotation could not be determined.

Oxamidodiphenylenebisiminocamphor (III).—The yellow crystalline compound obtained from the hydrochloride of diaminodiphenyl-oxamide (3.42 g.), prepared according to Mistry and Guha (*loc. cit.*), excess of sodium acetate and camphorquinone (3.5 g.) by boiling in 95% alcohol crystallised from alcohol in yellow shining leaflets, m.p.

183°_m (Found: N, 9.6. C₃₄H₃₈O₄N₄ requires N, 9.8 per cent). 0.103 G. of the substance in 25 c.c. chloroform in a 0.5 dm. tube gave $\alpha_D = +3.4^\circ$, whence $[\alpha]_D^{25} = 1650.4^\circ$ and $[M]_D = 9341.7^\circ$. 0.073 G. of the substance in 100 c.c. pyridine gave (0.5 dm. tube) $\alpha_D = 0.78^\circ$, whence $[\alpha]_D^{25} = 2136.9^\circ$ and $[M]_D = +12095$.

Thiocarbonylhydrazinocamphor.

Thiocarbohydrazide (1 mol.) and camphorquinone (2 mols.) were heated for 30 hours in absolute alcohol using anhydrous sodium sulphate as condensing agent. The yellow plates separating out on cooling, were washed successively with water and petrol and recrystallised from alcohol in yellowish-brown shining plates, m.p. 226°. (Found: S, 8.2. C₂₁H₃₀O₂N₄S requires S, 7.9 per cent). 0.94 G. of the substance dissolved in 100 c.c. chloroform gave in a 0.5 dm. tube $\alpha_D = +1.82^\circ$, whence $[M]_D = +1557^\circ$.

Condensation of 2:2'-diaminodiphenyl and 1:2-naphthylenediamine with camphorquinone could not be effected by the above methods.

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